

FROM THE KINEMATICS OF ELLIPTICAL MOTION TO THE GRAVITATIONAL FORCE

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Abstract

The law of the force governing the motion of a material point along an elliptical orbit is derived on the basis of a purely kinematic approach. Starting from the differential equations of motion in the Cartesian coordinate system, an angular equation of motion is obtained, which directly leads to Kepler's second law. It is shown that the acceleration is directed toward the focus of the ellipse and is inversely proportional to the square of the distance to it. The derivation is generalized to precessing orbits (rosettes) with an arbitrary parameter $k \neq 1$. The obtained expressions are applied to the Earth–Moon system. Forces calculated on the basis of Newton's second law are compared with the forces determined by the law of universal gravitation. The relative discrepancy does not exceed 1.2 %, which confirms the equivalence of the obtained expressions.

Keywords: kinematics, elliptical motion, Kepler's laws, orbital precession, Newton's second law, law of universal gravitation.

Introduction

The description of rectilinear motion can be obtained using elementary algebraic relations between position, velocity and acceleration. In contrast, the analysis of curvilinear motion of a material point requires the application of differential equations of motion. The specific method of their derivation depends on the chosen way of describing the motion.

The purpose of the present work is to derive the form of the force responsible for elliptical motion, proceeding exclusively from the kinematics of the trajectory without any preliminary assumption about the nature of the interaction.

Differential Equation of Motion Along an Ellipse Relative to the Focus

Consider the motion of a material point of mass m along an ellipse counterclockwise. One of the foci of the ellipse is located at the origin of a stationary Cartesian coordinate system. Let the force Q acting on the particle be directed toward the focus and form an angle $\varphi(t)$ with the X -axis. The equations of motion take the form:

$$m\ddot{x} = -Q\cos(\varphi(t)) \quad (1)$$

$$m\ddot{y} = -Q\sin(\varphi(t)) \quad (2)$$

From equation (1), expression (3) follows, which, after substitution into (2), yields equation (4):

$$Q = \frac{-m\ddot{x}}{\cos(\varphi(t))} \quad (3)$$

$$\ddot{y} = \frac{\ddot{x}}{\cos(\varphi(t))} \sin(\varphi(t)) \quad (4)$$

The coordinates of the point are represented as functions of the radius $r(t)$ and the angle of deflection $\varphi(t)$ (5) – (7):

$$x = r(\varphi(t))\cos(\varphi(t)), \quad y = r(\varphi(t))\sin(\varphi(t)) \quad (5)$$

$$r(\varphi(t)) = \frac{a(1-e^2)}{1+e\cdot\cos\varphi} \quad (6)$$

$$x = \frac{a(1-e^2)}{1+e\cdot\cos(\varphi(t))} \cos(\varphi(t)), \quad y = \frac{a(1-e^2)}{1+e\cdot\cos(\varphi(t))} \sin(\varphi(t)) \quad (7)$$

Differentiating the coordinates twice with respect to time yields expressions for velocity (8) – (12) and acceleration (13):

$$\dot{x} = \frac{d}{dt} \left(r(\varphi(t))\cos(\varphi(t)) \right) = \dot{r}\cos\varphi - r\sin\varphi \cdot \dot{\varphi} \quad (8)$$

$$\dot{y} = \frac{d}{dt} \left(r(\varphi(t))\sin(\varphi(t)) \right) = \dot{r}\sin\varphi + r\cos\varphi \cdot \dot{\varphi} \quad (9)$$

$$\ddot{x} = \frac{d^2}{dt^2} \left(r(\varphi(t))\cos(\varphi(t)) \right) = \ddot{r}\cos\varphi - 2\dot{r}\dot{\varphi}\sin\varphi - r\ddot{\varphi}\sin\varphi - r\dot{\varphi}^2\cos\varphi \quad (10)$$

$$\ddot{y} = \frac{d^2}{dt^2} \left(r(\varphi(t))\sin(\varphi(t)) \right) = \ddot{r}\sin\varphi + 2\dot{r}\dot{\varphi}\cos\varphi + r\ddot{\varphi}\cos\varphi - r\dot{\varphi}^2\sin\varphi \quad (11)$$

$$\text{velocity } v = \sqrt{\dot{x}^2 + \dot{y}^2} = \sqrt{\dot{r}^2 + (r\dot{\varphi})^2} \quad (12)$$

$$\text{acceleration } a = \sqrt{\ddot{x}^2 + \ddot{y}^2} = \sqrt{(\ddot{r} - r\dot{\varphi}^2)^2 + (2\dot{r}\dot{\varphi} + r\ddot{\varphi})^2} \quad (13)$$

The magnitude of the acceleration vector in polar coordinates has the standard form:

$$a_r = \ddot{r} - r\dot{\varphi}^2, \quad a_\varphi = 2\dot{r}\dot{\varphi} + r\ddot{\varphi}. \quad (14)$$

Derivation of Kepler's Laws

Substituting the second derivatives into equation (4) and moving the terms to the left side leads to equation (15). Solving it for $\ddot{\varphi}$ gives expression (16):

$$\frac{\ddot{x}}{\cos(\varphi(t))} \sin(\varphi(t)) - \ddot{y} = 0 \quad (15)$$

$$\ddot{\varphi} = -\frac{2\dot{r}\dot{\varphi}}{r} \quad (16)$$

Kepler's First Law: Kepler's first law is fulfilled a priori, as equation (16) describes motion along an ellipse.

Kepler's Second Law: Kepler's second law (the law of areas) states that the radius vector sweeps out equal areas in equal time intervals. In polar coordinates, this is written as (17). Integrating equation (16) leads to expression (18), where a constant of integration C arises. Formula (19) represents the analytical expression of the law of areas.

$$\frac{dA}{dt} = \frac{1}{2} r^2 \frac{d\varphi}{dt} = \text{const} \quad (17)$$

$$\dot{\varphi} = \frac{d\varphi}{dt} = \frac{C}{r^2} \quad (18)$$

$$\frac{dA}{dt} = \frac{1}{2} r^2 \frac{C}{r^2} = \frac{C}{2} = \text{const} \quad (19)$$

Analytical Derivation of the Law of Gravity

Using exclusively the kinematics of motion and the geometry of the ellipse:

- Motion occurs in a plane;
- The trajectory is an ellipse with a focus at the origin;
- Kepler's second law is satisfied.

The transverse (azimuthal) component of acceleration becomes zero, indicating the central nature of the force. After switching from time to the angular variable and substituting the ellipse equation, we obtain the expression for radial acceleration:

$$a_r \propto \frac{1}{r^2} \quad (20)$$

Consequently, the force has the form:

$$F(r) = ma_r = -\frac{mC^2}{p} \frac{1}{r^2} \quad (21)$$

By introducing the notation for the gravitational parameter, we obtain expression (22), which matches the form of Newton's law of universal gravitation:

$$F = \frac{GMm}{r^2} \quad (22)$$

Determination of the constant via the orbital period

Using the expression for angular velocity and the definition of the orbital period, we obtain the relation connecting the orbit parameter with the period of motion:

$$T = \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{r^2}{c} d\varphi = \frac{1}{c} \int_0^{2\pi} r^2 d\varphi \quad (23)$$

$$C = \frac{2\pi ab}{T} \quad (24)$$

Acceleration at apsidal points:

$$a_p = \frac{a^3 c^2 (1+e \cdot \cos \varphi)^2}{b^6} = \frac{a^3 c^2 (1+e)^2}{b^6} = \frac{c^2 (1+e)^2}{a^3 (1-e^2)^3} \quad (25)$$

$$a_a = \frac{c^2 (1+e \cdot \cos \varphi)^2}{a^3 (1-e^2)^3} = \frac{c^2 (1-e)^2}{a^3 (1-e^2)^3} = \frac{c^2 (1-e)^2}{a^3 (1-e^2)^3} \quad (26)$$

Numerical comparison for the Earth–Moon system We perform calculations of forces for the Moon's motion along an elliptical orbit using standard parameters (mass, semi-major axis, eccentricity, period) from NASA/JPL data for the Earth–Moon system.

Accelerations and forces are calculated at perigee and apogee. Forces are computed using Newton's second law and the law of universal gravitation:

$$a_{Mp}^{(kin)} = \frac{c_M^2 (1+e)^2}{a_M^3 (1-e^2)^3} \approx 3.05 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ m/s}^2 \quad (27)$$

$$a_{Ma}^{(kin)} = \frac{c_1^2 (1-e)^2}{a_M^3 (1-e^2)^3} \approx 2.45 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ m/s}^2 \quad (28)$$

$$F_{Ma}^{(kin)} = M_M a_{Ma}^{(kin)} \approx 1.80 \cdot 10^{20} \text{ N} \quad (29)$$

$$F_{Mp}^{(kin)} = M_M a_{Mp}^{(kin)} \approx 2.24 \cdot 10^{20} \text{ N} \quad (30)$$

$$F_p^{(grav)} = G \frac{M_M M_E}{r_p^2} \approx 2.22 \cdot 10^{20} \text{ N} \quad (31)$$

$$F_a^{(grav)} = G \frac{M_M M_E}{r_a^2} \approx 1.78 \cdot 10^{20} \text{ N} \quad (32)$$

The relative error does not exceed 1.2%:

$$\delta_p = \frac{F_{Mp}^{(kin)} - F_p^{(grav)}}{F_{Mp}^{(kin)}} = \frac{2.24 - 2.22}{2.24} 100\% \approx 0.89\% \quad (33)$$

$$\delta_a = \frac{F_{Ma}^{(kin)} - F_a^{(grav)}}{F_{Ma}^{(kin)}} = \frac{1.80 - 1.78}{1.80} 100\% \approx 1.11\% \quad (34)$$

Since the motion parameters of the Moon and Earth are related by the ratio

$$\frac{M_M}{M_E} = \frac{a_E^{(kin)}}{a_M^{(kin)}} = \frac{a_E}{a_M}, \quad (35)$$

we also calculate the radii, accelerations, and forces for the motion of the Earth's center of mass at perigee and apogee:

$$a_E = \frac{M_M a_M}{M_E} = 4728167 \approx 4.73 \cdot 10^6 \text{ m} \quad (36)$$

$$C_E = \frac{2\pi a_E^2 \sqrt{1-e^2}}{T} \approx 3.93 \cdot 10^{11} \text{ m}^2/\text{s} \quad (37)$$

$$a_{Ep}^{(kin)} = \frac{C_E^2 (1+e)^2}{a_E^3 (1-e^2)^3} \approx 3.75 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ m/s}^2 \quad (38)$$

$$a_{Ea}^{(kin)} = \frac{C_E^2 (1-e)^2}{a_E^3 (1-e^2)^3} \approx 3.01 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ m/s}^2 \quad (39)$$

$$F_{Ep}^{(kin)} = M_E a_{Ep}^{(kin)} \approx 2.24 \cdot 10^{20} \text{ N} \quad (40)$$

$$F_{Ea}^{(kin)} = M_E a_{Ea}^{(kin)} \approx 1.80 \cdot 10^{20} \text{ N} \quad (41)$$

The illusion of a contradiction between Newton's laws It is sometimes suggested that there is a contradiction between Newton's second law and the law of universal gravitation. The argument is as follows: if the force is directed strictly toward the focus of the orbit, it has no tangential component, and therefore the speed should not change. However, during elliptical motion the magnitude of velocity varies at different points of the orbit.

The reason for this apparent contradiction lies in the difference between the bases used for decomposing acceleration.

In the polar coordinate system with a central force, the azimuthal component of acceleration is zero, leading to conservation of angular momentum and fulfillment of Kepler's second law.

In the Frenet basis (tangential and normal to the trajectory), a radially directed force generally has a non-zero projection onto the velocity direction (except at

apsidal points). It is precisely this projection that causes the change in the magnitude of velocity.

Thus, there is no contradiction between Newton's second law and the law of universal gravitation: the former establishes the relation between force and acceleration, while the latter specifies the particular form of the force.

Precession

For any central field (azimuthal acceleration component = 0).

Radial acceleration in polar coordinates (formula 14).

We change to the independent variable φ (instead of t). Denote the derivative with respect to φ by a prime:

$$\dot{r} = r' \dot{\varphi}, \quad \ddot{r} = r'' \dot{\varphi}^2 + r' \ddot{\varphi},$$

Substituting $\ddot{\varphi}$ from (16):

$$\ddot{\varphi} = -\frac{2r' \dot{\varphi}^2}{r}.$$

Then:

$$a_r = \dot{\varphi}^2 \left(r'' - \frac{2(r')^2}{r} - r \right).$$

It is more convenient to introduce $u(\varphi) = 1/r(\varphi)$. Then $\dot{\varphi} = Cu^2$,

$$\dot{r} = -Cu', \quad \ddot{r} = -C^2 u^2 u''.$$

This yields the exact kinematic **Binet formula**:

$$a_r = -C^2 u^2 \left(\frac{d^2 u}{d\varphi^2} + u \right). \quad (42)$$

(This formula is derived strictly from (16) and the definition of a_r , without any assumptions about the law of force.)

Now, we generalize the trajectory (instead of the standard ellipse (6)):

$$r(\varphi) = \frac{p}{1+e \cdot \cos(k\varphi)}, \quad p = a(1 - e^2). \quad (43)$$

Here, $k = 1$ represents a closed ellipse, while $k \neq 1$ represents a precessing rosette.

$$u(\varphi) = \frac{1+e \cdot \cos(k\varphi)}{p}. \quad (44)$$

Derivatives:

$$\frac{du}{d\varphi} = -\frac{ek}{p} \sin(k\varphi), \quad \frac{d^2u}{d\varphi^2} = -\frac{ek^2}{p} \cos(k\varphi).$$

The sum:

$$\frac{d^2u}{d\varphi^2} + u = \frac{k^2}{p} + (1 - k^2)u.$$

Substituting this back:

$$a_r = C^2 u^2 \left(\frac{k^2}{p} + (1 - k^2)u \right) = -\frac{C^2 k^2}{pr^2} - C^2 (1 - k^2) \frac{1}{r^3}. \quad (45)$$

Force (Newton's Second Law):

$$F(r) = ma_r = -\frac{mC^2 k^2}{pr^2} - mC^2 (1 - k^2) \frac{1}{r^3}, \quad (46)$$

Special Cases

$$\text{When } k = 1: F(r) = -\frac{mC^2}{pr^2} \quad (47)$$

identical to (21)).

When $k = 1 - \varepsilon$, ($\varepsilon \ll 1$):

$$F(r) \approx -\frac{mC^2 k^2}{pr^2} + 2m \frac{C^2 \varepsilon}{r^3}. \quad (48)$$

Precession angle per revolution:

$$\Delta\varphi = 2\pi \left(\frac{1}{k} - 1 \right) \approx 2\pi\varepsilon. \quad (49)$$

All numerical calculations for the Earth–Moon system (pp. 5–6) carry over unchanged when $k = 1$. For the real precession of the Moon's perigee (period ≈ 8.85 years), $k \approx 0.9916$ ($\Delta\varphi \approx 3^\circ$ per revolution), but the comparison error with the gravitation law remains $< 1.2\%$ (the Moon's precession is caused by perturbations, not by a change in the force law).

Conclusion

Analysis of the kinematics of motion along an ellipse allows us to establish that acceleration consists of tangential and normal components.

When the coordinate origin is placed at the focus of the ellipse, acceleration is directed toward the focus, indicating the central character of the force.

Centrality of the force is equivalent to the absence of the azimuthal acceleration component and leads to conservation of angular momentum.

The absence of azimuthal acceleration does not mean the absence of a tangential component in the Frenet basis.

The combined application of Newton's second law and the law of universal gravitation leads to conic-section orbits consistent with Kepler's laws.

Newton's second law is a universal dynamical principle, while the law of universal gravitation is a particular case of a central force.

References

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